

Neurodiverse Students Learning in Large Lecture Theatres: Challenges and Opportunities

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Abstract

This paper explores the impact of massification in higher education, particularly in large classroom settings, on students who identify as neurodivergent. It focuses on how these students navigate learning in such environments and examines pedagogical practices that may affect their inclusion and learning outcomes. The author, with experience teaching classes of various sizes in higher education, notes the challenges that arise when neurodivergent characteristics clash with the demands of large classrooms. Neurodiversity encompasses a range of neurological challenges. This paper aims to investigate how these challenges intersect with large class settings and impact teaching and learning dynamics and considers strategies to maximise engagement, participation and learning for neurodiverse students in large higher education classes.

Keywords: *Neurodivergent; Large classroom; Inclusion; Pedagogical practices*

1. Introduction

This paper explores how students who identify as neurodivergent navigate university large classroom settings in relation to their learning. Neurodiversity is an umbrella term for a range of different neurological challenges. These can be referred to as specific learning difficulties and development disorders which can include dyslexia, dyspraxia, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, dyscalculia, autistic spectrum, and Tourette syndrome. The term large is often contested (Kerr, 2011) and there is no accepted definition of what a large class is although ‘studies in this area tend to draw evidence from classes with more than 100 students’ (Maringe & Sing, 2014: 763). However, in this paper, large will be used in relation to if, when or how this impedes on the learning and teaching of a student who is neurodiverse. Consequently, the focus will be on pedagogical practices which may or may not be appropriate for this student cohort and their teaching, learning and inclusion in the educational setting. The author has taught classes of varying sizes of 20, 60 and up to 118 students in higher education, which had neurotypical and neurodivergent students. The characteristics of being neurodivergent can often create issues for teaching and learning in large classes. Difficulties with reading speed, note taking, spelling, proof-reading, deciphering academic language at speed and memory retrieval are all common characteristics of having dyslexia and are skills which are often needed in a large and often noisy classroom. According to Vincent *et. al.* (2017) students with neurodiversity constantly feel out of place and this can be exacerbated by large, busy, and noisy spaces.

2. Description of the Teaching/Learning Context

Large classrooms are increasing within higher education, particularly where an institution uses neoliberal criteria of optimal revenue, profitability and financial sustainability as prime objectives for quality assurance and strategic development (Minz, 2021). The university in this context is a Technological University, which teaches mainly applied courses, where graduates are considered ‘job ready’ when they are finished, and ninety percent of the student cohort enter directly following completion of secondary school. One of the most difficult experiences for these students can be the transition from a formal school setting to a higher education institution which can be a daunting prospect for all students. Class sizes consisted of between 100 to 120 students and contact was a three-hour lecture for each module a week in a social care class. These courses are applied and require a more ‘hands on’ approach which may be difficult to achieve in large classes. Teaching practices used were what Freire (1970) described as the banking method, whereby I stood at the top of a lecture theatre and imparted content. In contrast with using teaching strategies which encourage student participation and engagement such as, group or pair tasks, posing questions and using multimedia, didactic and transmissive approaches to teaching and learning which for example could include the lecturer standing at a podium and talking at students, can often be non-productive in this environment and students can become easily lost, especially those

students who identify as neurodivergent. Moreover, this approach severely limited student participation and engagement, developing connections or relationships, and ultimately affected attendance. One of the main issues identified in research by Murphy (2023) was the lack of knowledge around neurodiversity and how it affects learning by academic staff and their peers. Students who are neurodiverse pose a particular challenge to academic staff because their difficulties are hidden, and they are often lost in the large class environment.

In large classrooms or lecture halls, the challenges for neurodiverse students may be intensified (Jacobs *et al*, 2020). Using the traditional banking (Freire, 1970) 'talk-at-them' approach to teaching, students became bored, started to talk among themselves, and use their phones and consequently the noise levels increased in the room and over-stimulation became heightened making it even more difficult for neurodiverse students to learn in the large groups in these 3-hour long lectures. High noise levels made it difficult for students to concentrate and focus on the content being presented. This was especially true for students who were sensitive to auditory distractions or who had difficulty filtering out background noise. These large group classrooms were also over-stimulating, with various visual and auditory stimuli competing for students' attention. This often led to sensory overload and distracted students from the learning objectives. During the last class of each semester, an overview and review of the year and discussions around final assessments are usually held. This generally led to high attendance and engagement from students. I always tried to take advantage of this high attendance to ask the students to complete a short feedback sheet with four simple questions in order for me to try and improve the content and teaching and learning for those students following on next term. I found this was a much better way to record findings within such a large class than an end of module survey completed outside of class. I would ask the students 'what did you like/dislike about this module' and a large proportion of the feedback would relate to: 'class too noisy', 'too much chitter/chatter', 'can't think', and more comments like this which related to the environment. All the discussion above led me to reflect on my pedagogy and implement some changes within my practices.

3. Literature Review

Cook-Sather *et al*. (2014), Dunne (2016), and Mercer-Mapstone *et al*. (2017) discuss the concept of 'students as partners' and how the notion of co-created learning and teaching has gained traction in higher education. This notion encompasses various levels of involvement and implies a deeper level of student engagement and agency emphasising "collaboration between students and educators, where students are actively involved in the design, delivery, and assessment of their learning experiences" (Bovill, 2020, p. 1024). Student engagement encompasses involvement in both learning and teaching processes, as well as participation in student representation and governance structures according to Bovill (2020). Nonetheless, while both student engagement and students as partners involve student involvement, as well as a greater level of collaboration and shared responsibility between students and educators

in shaping the learning experience, this may present particular challenges within large class environments.

According to Altbach (2009) and Maringe and Sing (2014), ‘momentum around increased participation and student mobility in higher education in an increasingly globalising world is gathering pace and, in the process, changing both the demography and size of university classrooms’ (Maringe & Sing, 2014: 761). These changes have implications and consequences for the quality and equity of learning and pedagogical practices. Although there is literature relating to teaching large classes, the challenge that is emerging in higher education is how these impact on students from diverse backgrounds. Consequently, large class sizes have become not just about numbers, they are also related to the complexities and challenges of delivering both equality and quality learning opportunities for all students.

There is little evidence at present to suggest an ideal class size for effective university learning. According to Cuseo (2004), there is evidence which suggests diminishing returns in terms of opportunities to learn as class sizes increase and a 2018 report by the European University Association (2018) noted that ‘teaching in small groups was found useful by practically all institutions’ (Gaebel & Zhang, 2018: 55). AHEAD (2021) suggests that half of the students registered with a disability in higher education in Ireland are neurodiverse and many of the challenges they face can be exacerbated in a large class size environment. These larger environments can often overwhelm neurodiverse students, and this will not ensure a truly inclusive learning environment according to Miciak & Flecher (2020).

Larger classrooms can be equally as challenging for instructors as well as students due to the pace and demands. The Universal Design for Learning (UDL) model which is underpinned by the three UDL principles of engagement, representation, and action and expression (CAST, 2011; AHEAD, 2021) promotes an inclusive model for students of all abilities and provides high quality individual supports for those students who need them. UDL ensures support services are funded ‘to engage in delivering quality-assured reasonable accommodations, and to collaborate across campus and promote more inclusive practice in the mainstream delivery of programmes’ (AHEAD, 2021:5). This model was developed using the voices of students, academic staff, management, and student support staff which ensures their three principles underpin the delivery of the programme or as Franklin phrased it: ‘Involve me and I will learn’. Nonetheless, Fovet, (2021) found that even among UDL advocates and implementers in higher education (HE), there has been some hesitation when it comes to implementing and using UDL in large class contexts.

4. Analysis of/Reflection on/Implications for Practice

As an educator I reflected on the traditional methods of teaching I was using in these larger learning and teaching spaces and how I might make them more inclusive for neurodiverse students. I wondered how I might create a learning environment that is inclusive for all

students, regardless of the class size. How I might better engage all of the students all of the time or even some of the time, would it be feasible to use the Universal Design for Learning model in this space, or if applied courses are being taught, courses that require discussions around sometimes sensitive material and experiential learning? Although Nieminen (2021) found that it can be almost impossible to achieve a curriculum that tackles the needs of all learners, upon reflection of my own pedagogy practices, I decided to implement some changes to make my classrooms as inclusive as possible.

4.1 Teaching Practices

According to Sanger (2020) large classes give rise to specific pedagogical challenges, particularly in relation to inclusion and accessibility. This is where I decided to try and implement change to make my classrooms more inclusive and accessible. With the support of our department, school, and university, we made some changes to how we delivered content. The three-hour lecture was changed to a one hour and thirty-minute class. The content and theory on the day's topic was delivered to the whole class group and then the whole class was divided into four groups of 28 students in one hour tutorial style classes. Students reported back that this worked better as they received the content in the whole group, however, when they sat in the smaller groups, it provided a space for the applied work to be carried out in a safe space, the discussion was meaningful and that they learned better.

Some other pedagogy changes I made revolved around the content I was using. I used less text in my PowerPoints, included more images and used more visuals. All my notes on our shared learning spaces were changed to Word documents so students could edit as they saw fit. I released the PowerPoint the day before our classes, as opposed to the hour after the lectures. This can offer neurodiverse students and indeed all students the opportunity to study these ideas and new concepts before they encounter them for the first time in the large class environment. This allowed students to view the content and examine any words or theory they were not familiar with before the classroom lecture. The reason for this is that neurodiverse students can get lost very easily in lectures when they are trying to decipher content for the first time and become very frustrated and detached when they cannot catch up.

Informed by students' input and their feedback, changes to assessments were made. The traditional two academic essay style assessments were replaced with a presentation type assessment whereby students worked in groups of four and presented the content to their small group. This could be through a PowerPoint, a video, role play or any other means which was discussed with and agreed with me. The second assessment was a traditional style academic essay using a brief from the lecturer and the end of term assessment was a short multiple choice questionnaire on the topics covered. This changing of the assessments proved to be easy to implement as the module was 100% continuous assessment. The students enjoyed this process as they felt they had some control over their learning and how they were assessed.

4.2 Other Changes

I also changed all my material to font style Verdana, which my research in 2021 found to be the preferred font (Murphy, 2022). Students fed back that this worked very well for them. Some other changes I made were including some voice content on each slide, a brief recording on the assessments to bring clarity and leaving content accessible until after the student's exams were completed. Links to short YouTube videos and other varying resources were also reported to be helpful. Nonetheless, in the larger spaces, students still reported issues with note taking, comprehension and memory recalling of specific subject-related academic language due to the nature of the large space. Some ways I compensated for this was through the use of assistive technology in lectures. Voice overs on the slides on Moodle allowed students to use listening devices so they could hear the discussion around the PowerPoints at the minimum in the classroom and they could be used outside the classroom for the duration of the module. After discussion in the classroom with the students, they were allowed on their phones only for them to use their devices for listening to the slides and/or searching for words they did not understand. We agreed to commit to a non-share with others of any recordings from my modules and some students also used a LiveScribe pen in my lectures.

I found these UDL principles difficult to implement within the larger class due to time constraints, disturbances, attention, and the effort it often took. However, within the smaller tutorial style setting where the applied parts of the course were delivered, UDL was much easier to incorporate within the teaching and learning environment. This allowed both myself and the students greater representation through being more visible and accessible in the classroom. Engagement between students and the learning increased also and the discussions were very beneficial to all. Action and expression was very evident then due to the discussions, building of personal connections with the learners and allowing students to demonstrate their skills and competencies in multiple ways.

5. Conclusions

The implementation of a state-wide awareness and educational campaign around neurodiversity and inclusiveness is important. University staff and academic staff need to be given continuous professional development on neurodiverse differences, what they are, what they are not, how it affects a student's educational experience and what can be done to develop a more inclusive classroom. It would also be beneficial to implement strategies and technology to minimise noise within large classrooms to create more inclusive and accessible learning experiences that support the diverse needs of all students.

Whether classes are large or small, educators can consider creating structured learning activities that help students stay focused and engaged, breaking down content into smaller, digestible chunks, incorporating interactive elements, and providing opportunities for

movement or hands-on learning. Incorporating feedback from students and developing options for students to customise their learning experiences can help accommodate diverse needs and preferences.

Implementing inclusive teaching practices can help create a supportive learning environment for all students, regardless of their sensory sensitivities. This may involve incorporating UDL principles into course materials and activities, such as providing multiple modes of representation, expression, and engagement (CAST, 2011). Additionally, fostering a culture of respect and understanding among students can encourage empathy and support for other students who may experience sensory challenges.

References

- AHEAD. (2021). Launch of Students with Disabilities Engaged with Support Services in Third level education in Ireland 2019/20 Report. Dublin: AHEAD Educational Press.
- Altbach, P. G. (2009). Peripheries and centres: Research universities in developing countries. *Asia Pacific Education Review*. 10: 5–27.
- Bovill, C. (2020). Co-creation in learning and teaching: the case for a whole-class approach in higher education. *Higher Education*. 79:1023–1037.
- CAST (Centre for Applied Special Technology). (2011). Universal Design for Learning Guidelines Version 2.0. Wakefield, MA: National Centre on Universal Design for Learning. Retrieved from:
<https://www.cast.org/impact/universal-design-for-learning-udl>
(Accessed on 26/03/2024).
- Cook-Sather, A. (2014). Listening to equity-seeking perspectives: how students' experiences of pedagogical partnership can inform wider discussions of student success. *Higher Education Research and Development*. 37(5), 923–936.
- Cuseo, J. (2004). The empirical case against large class size: adverse effects on the teaching, learning, and retention of first-year students. *The Journal of Faculty Development*. 21: 5–21.
- Dunne, E. (2016). Design thinking: a framework for student engagement? A personal view. *Journal of Educational Innovation, Partnership and Change*. 2(1).
- Fovet, F. (2021). Including learner diversity in large class teaching - Using Universal Design for Learning to sustain a systematic proactive reflection on social justice and accessibility. Proceedings of the Pedagogy for Higher Education Large Classes 2022 Conference (PHELC22), 2022.
- Freire, P. (1970). *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*. New York: Continuum Press.
- Gaebel, M., Zang, T., Bunescu, L, & Strober, H. (2018). Trends 2018, Learning and teaching in the European Higher Education Area. Creative Commons Attribution: Belgium.

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- Jacobs, L., Parke, A., Ziegler, F., Headleand, C & De Angeli, A. (2020). Learning at school through to university: the educational experiences of students with dyslexia at one UK higher education institution. *Disability & Society*. 3:1-22.
- Kerr, A. (2011). *Teaching and Learning in Large Classes at Ontario Universities: An Exploratory Study*. Toronto: Higher Education Quality Council of Ontario.
- Maringe, F, and Sing, N. (2014). Teaching large classes in an increasingly internationalising higher education environment: pedagogical, quality and equity issues. *High Education*. 67:761–782
- Mercer-Mapstone, L., Dvorakova, S. L., Matthews, K. E., Abbot, S., Cheng, B., Felten, P., Knorr, C., Marquis, E., Shamma, R., & Swaim, K. (2017). A systematic literature review of students as partners in higher education. *International Journal for Students as Partners*. 1:1–23.
- Miciak, J, & Flecher, J. (2020). The Critical Role of Instructional Response for Identifying Dyslexia and Other Learning Disabilities. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*. 53: 343-353.
- Minz, B. (2021) Neoliberalism and the Crisis in Higher Education: The Cost of Ideology. *American Journal of Economics and Sociology*, 80: 79-112.
- Murphy, K. (2022). Studying with dyslexia and achieving in partnership with it in higher education. A Review of Inclusive Education and Employment Practices. *The AHEAD Journal*. 15 (5):23-30.
- Murphy, K. (2023). Experiencing Dyslexia through the Prism of Difference. REACH: *Journal of Inclusive Education in Ireland*. DOI: 10.21427/RJ38-AM92.
- Nieminen, J. (2021). Governing the disabled assessee’: a critical reframing of assessment accommodations as sociocultural practices. *Disability and Society*. 10: 1-28.
- Sanger, C.S. (2020). Inclusive Pedagogy and Universal Design Approaches for Diverse Learning Environments. In: Sanger, C. and Gleason, N. (Eds) *Diversity and Inclusion in Global Higher Education*. Palgrave Macmillan. London.
- Vincent, J., Potts, M., Fletcher, D., Hodges, S., Howells, J., Mitchell, A., Mallon, B., & Ledger, T. (2017). ‘I think autism is like running on windows while everyone else is a mac’: using a participatory action research approach with students on the autistic spectrum to rearticulate autism and the lived experience of university. *Educational Action Research*. 25:300– 315.